

LLM assisted RE: Pre-workshop Interview

The purpose of this interview is to understand the case company's existing RE processes, the challenges & limitations faced during these processes and practitioner's perception of how LLMs can possibly help them overcome the limitations.

* Required

1. What do you know about large language models (LLMs)? *

2. What motivated you to consider LLMs as an option to address these challenges and/or improve your current processes? *

3. How do you plan to conduct the quality evaluation of the outputs (generated RE artefacts) of the LLMs? *

4. What do you plan to improve by using these LLM based techniques in your RE processes? *

5. How do you plan to measure the improvement (if any) in your processes? *

6. What is the most important characteristic you look for in these LLM based techniques? *

- User friendliness
- Quality of the outputs
- Ease of integration into existing processes
- Other

7. There is a risk that the RE artefacts generated using LLMs might be similar (in some ways) to RE artefacts of other organisations that use LLMs in a similar way to yours. Would that be an issue? If yes, how? *

8. What are the ethical and legal aspects of LLMs being incorporated into your practices that you are worried about? How do you plan address them? *

9. What do you understand by the term "Prompt Engineering?" *

10. How much do you know about prompt engineering? *

- No Idea
- Heard about it but lack any technical understanding
- Have a theoretical understanding of the concept and know some prompt engineering techniques
- I know a lot of prompt engineering techniques and patterns and I regularly implement them whenever I'm using an LLM

11. Do you have strategy in mind for the choice of prompt engineering techniques you want to use to interact with the LLMs during the workshop? *

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